

A Comparison of the Exchange Behaviour of Tris-trimethylene diamine Co(III) onto Montmorillonite and Laponite and Its Release by Tetraalkylammonium, Alkanediammonium and Long Chain Surface Active Ions

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The nature of the exchange isotherms of tris-trimethylene diamine Co(III) onto Na-montmorillonite and Na-Laponite together with the desorption data of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from the clay matrices by different organic ions reveals that $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ is more strongly bound in Na-montmorillonite than in Na-Laponite, a synthetic hectorite, which may be attributed to the higher charge density of the former mineral. The release of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from both the clay surfaces follows the order $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+ > (\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17})_4\text{N}^+ > (\text{C}_6\text{H}_{13})_4\text{N}^+ > (\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ upto certain exchange levels beyond which a reversal of the sequence is observed. The desorption efficiency of the long-chain surfactants and alkane diammonium ions increases with chain length in both the minerals. The smaller tetraalkylammonium and alkanediammonium ions release more $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ than the larger surfactants from the montmorillonite complex while in Laponite the situation is just the opposite. The selectivity coefficients of the long chain monovalent ions are higher than the bivalent short chained ions or tetraalkylammonium ions for both the minerals, suggesting that for ion exchange reactions involving organic ions, size is more important than charge.

ION exchange studies on different clay minerals have revealed the importance of charge density in exchange selectivity^{1,2} as well as in the orientation of the adsorbed organic cations³. The effect of charge density of the clay minerals on the competitive adsorption by ion exchange of two divalent organic cations viz. diquat (1,1'-ethylene-2,2'-dipyridinium ion) and paraquat (1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-dipyridinium ion) was studied by Weed and Weber¹. They noted that the adsorption of the organic ions by external surfaces of vermiculite and mica appeared to be linearly related to the surface charge densities of the adsorbents. Charge density of the clay mineral may also affect the orientation of the adsorbed organic cations through steric effects. For example, Serratos³ showed by infrared absorption technique that in pyridinium-montmorillonite the organic cation assumed an orientation where the plane of the pyridine ring was parallel with the platelets of the clay while in pyridinium-vermiculite the pyridinium cations were oriented vertically with respect to the clay platelets. It is apparent that the close proximity of the cation exchange sites one to another in vermiculite prevents the pyridinium ion from assuming the parallel position because of the restricted area permitted for each pyridinium ion.

In view of the dependence of the ion exchange phenomena on the type of clay minerals as well as on their charge characteristics, the sorption behaviour of tris-1,3-propane diamine Co(III) or tris-

trimethylene diamine Co(III) i.e. $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ onto the montmorillonite and Na-Laponite (a synthetic hectorite having charge density lower than that of montmorillonite) and their desorption from the clay matrices have been investigated with a number of tetraalkylammonium ions, long-chain surface active ions and alkane diammonium ions to obtain further insight in this field.

Experimental

The synthetic hectorite used in this investigation was Na-Laponite XLG, supplied in powder form by Laporte Industries Ltd., U.K. To ensure complete saturation with sodium, it was leached several times with 1 N NaCl solution and then dialysed against distilled water until free of chloride. The montmorillonite was obtained from Evans Medical Ltd., Liverpool, England and clay fractions of $< 2.0 \mu\text{m}$ particle sizes were isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation. After removal of organic matter by treatment with H_2O_2 , the montmorillonite was converted into its Na-form by appropriate treatment with Na-resin (Dowex 50X \times 8) and OH^- saturated resin (Dowex 2 \times 8).

The exchange of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ on Na-montmorillonite and Na-Laponite was studied by taking 10 ml of each clay suspension in several pyrex bottles and adding different amounts of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3\text{Cl}_3$ solution to

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each bottle. The bottles were shaken for about 2 hr and allowed to equilibrate overnight. These were then centrifuged (10,000 rpm) for about 15 min and $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3\text{Cl}_3$ content was estimated from absorbance measurements of the supernatant liquids using a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer. For desorption studies $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ saturated Na-montmorillonite and Na-Laponite were prepared by adding $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3\text{Cl}_3$ solutions in concentrations approximately 300 me/100 g of clay. The excess salt was washed out after 24 hr until the leachate had zero optical density. The resulting clay was then redispersed in distilled water. The concentrations of the Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -montmorillonite and Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Laponite suspensions used for desorption studies were 2.119 and 2.182 % (w/v), respectively and were determined by drying a definite volume at 105° for 24 hr. For desorption studies 10 ml portions of the suspension were taken in a number of pyrex bottles and varying amounts of different electrolytes were added. The total volumes were adjusted to 15 ml by adding requisite amounts of distilled water. The bottles with their contents were shaken for 2 hr and kept overnight to attain equilibrium. The mixtures were centrifuged (10,000 rpm) for ~ 15 min and the $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3\text{Cl}_3$ content was estimated colorimetrically as above.

Results and Discussion

Although Laponite, a synthetic trioctahedral smectite that owes its charge to octahedral replacement of Mg by Li, and montmorillonite are members of the expanding three layer clays, the former has lower charge density than the latter⁴. The exchange capacities of Na-montmorillonite and Na-Laponite are 100 and 85 meq/100 g clay, respectively. The nitrogen sorption surface areas of Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -montmorillonite and Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Laponite, which measure mostly the interlamellar areas⁵ are $261 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $280 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, respectively. The data therefore suggest that Na-montmorillonite possesses higher charge density than Na-Laponite.

The exchange isotherms and the corresponding linear Langmuir plots of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ sorption onto Na-montmorillonite and Na-Laponite are shown in Fig. 1. The maximum uptake of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ corresponds to 112 meq and 85 meq/100 g for the two clays, respectively. Both the isotherms are of the H-type as defined by Giles *et al*⁶, representing a very high affinity between the adsorbate and the adsorbent, but the knee of the isotherm is steeper in montmorillonite. This signifies that $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ cations have relatively higher affinity for the montmorillonite and may be related to the higher charge density of the mineral compared to Laponite^{1,2,4}. As the charge on $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ is the same for both the systems, it is the variation of the surface charge density of the adsorbents which primarily causes the difference in the preference of adsorption. Further, the calculated Langmuir bonding constants for the adsorption isotherms are 133.0 and 57.0 for montmorillonite and Laponite, respectively. The higher value of the constant also

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherms and Langmuir plots of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3\text{Cl}_3$ on Na-montmorillonite (a,d) and on Na-Laponite (b,c).

suggests stronger binding of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ in the former mineral as the Langmuir bonding constant is directly proportional to the heat of adsorption⁷.

The percentages of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ released from Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -montmorillonite and Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Laponite by tetraalkylammonium ions are presented in Figs. 2 and 3. It is noted that in the initial stages

Fig. 2. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -montmorillonite by tetraalkylammonium ions.

Fig. 3. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from Na- $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Laponite by tetraalkylammonium ions.

of the isotherms the preference of the tetraalkylammonium ions for both the minerals increases with the size of the ions. This could be related to the greater contribution of physical, non-coulombic forces to adsorption energy as the size of the ions increases⁸ and also to the changes in the hydration

states of the ions in the clay interlayers^{2,9}. However, the selectivity of the organic ions for the clay surfaces is reversed after certain level of exchange for each ion and the effect is more prominent in the case of montmorillonite than that of Laponite. The results may be explained by assuming contraction of the silicate layers in suspension once a critical level of surface coverage by the large tetraalkylammonium ions has been attained^{10,11}. Due to this collapse of the layers, the $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ ions which are entrapped in the interlayers become inaccessible for exchange as further diffusion of the tetraalkylammonium ions into the interlamellar region is restricted. This effect is, therefore, expected to increase as the size of the tetraalkylammonium ions increases because the larger $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{N}^+$ having a coverage area¹² of 110.0 \AA^2 would fill most of the interlayer volume than would the smaller $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}^+$ with an area¹² of 31.0 \AA^2 . As a consequence, at higher concentrations of the electrolytes the exchanging efficiency is inversely related to size of the organic ions especially in montmorillonite. However, due to its lower charge density, the attractive forces between the clay platelets are less in Laponite and as a result it can swell more freely than montmorillonite in aqueous medium. So the space and steric factors for the accommodation of large organic ions assume less importance in Laponite and exchange can take place more easily with the organic ions. The contraction effect vis-a-vis the reversal of selectivity of the tetraalkylammonium ions at higher concentrations are, therefore, less marked in this mineral than in montmorillonite.

The exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from its montmorillonite and Laponite complexes by large surface active ions such as decyltrimethylammonium (DTA), dodecyltrimethylammonium (DDTA), cetyltrimethylammonium (CTA), cetylpyridinium (CP) and alkane diammonium ions like ethane diammonium (EDA), $\text{H}_3\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{NH}_3^+$, and 1,3-propane diammonium (PrDA), $\text{H}_3\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3^+$, are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The amount of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ release from the clay matrices increases with the chain length of the surfactants and alkane diammo-

Fig. 4. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -montmorillonite by alkanediammonium and surface active ions.

Fig. 5. Exchange isotherms of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ from $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -Laponite by alkanediammonium and surface active ions.

nium ions and may be related to the increased contribution of the van der Waals force to the adsorption energy⁸ as well as changes in the hydration status of the ions in the clay interlayers^{2,9}. This behaviour would be expected for a flat orientation of the organic ions onto the clay surface as van der Waals type of interactions are additive and therefore would progressively increase with the size of the interacting species.

It is interesting to note that in montmorillonite system the smaller tetraalkylammonium and alkane diammonium ions desorb much more $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ than the larger CTA^+ or CP^+ while in Laponite the reverse effect is observed. The findings may be rationalised by considering the difference in the distance between two charge centres of the minerals and the greater swelling properties of Laponite. Due to its higher surface charge density than Laponite, the exchange sites in montmorillonite are more closely spaced than the latter and therefore the possibility of the covering up effect of some of the exchange sites by the large surface active ions in flat orientation¹³ appears to be more probable in montmorillonite. As a result, a fraction of the $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ ions initially adsorbed in montmorillonite remains inaccessible for exchange by the larger surface active ions.

The exchange isotherms reveal that the percentages of $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ desorption by the organic ions are much higher from Laponite than from montmorillonite suggesting that $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ is more strongly bound in the latter due to its higher charge density². On the other hand, the organic ions are adsorbed in larger quantities by Laponite than montmorillonite. According to Vansant and Peeters⁴ the hydration of alkylammonium ions is lowered on adsorption in clay interlayer and the extent of such lowering is more pronounced in Laponite than in montmorillonite. Therefore, van der Waals force would be more effective in Laponite causing large organic ions to be adsorbed.

The distribution and selectivity coefficients of the desorbing organic ions (Table I) have been calculated as in a previous publication¹⁴. These coeffi-

coefficients are higher in Laponite suggesting that $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ ions are less strongly bound in Laponite than in montmorillonite. Interestingly, the selectivity coefficients of the long chain surface active ions, CTA^+

TABLE 1—DESORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF $\text{Co}(\text{tn})_3^{3+}$ FROM $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -MONTMORILLONITE (B) AND $\text{Na-Co}(\text{tn})_3$ -LAPONITE (L) BY DIFFERENT ORGANIC IONS

Electrolyte	Concentration of electrolyte <i>M</i>	Distribution Coefficient		Selectivity Coefficient	
		(B)	(L)	(B)	(L)
$(\text{OH}_2)_4\text{NCl}$	4.0×10^{-3}	9.79	11.33	1.92	2.34
	6.0×10^{-3}	8.20	10.14	1.87	2.51
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	4.0×10^{-3}	14.36	17.34	3.69	4.63
	6.0×10^{-3}	10.17	11.62	2.25	3.17
$(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7)_4\text{NI}$	4.0×10^{-3}	16.48	16.31	4.28	4.76
	6.0×10^{-3}	11.24	10.86	3.0	3.24
$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{NBr}$	2.0×10^{-3}	26.74	33.33	5.84	9.36
	4.0×10^{-3}	14.42	16.34	3.41	5.13
DTABr	5.0×10^{-3}	65.44	117.10	10.43	24.80
	10.0×10^{-3}	64.40	73.61	14.75	20.69
DDTABr	5.0×10^{-3}	76.29	124.65	12.32	27.25
	10.0×10^{-3}	72.48	77.50	17.13	22.64
CTABr	5.0×10^{-3}	100.29	140.40	18.41	32.65
	10.0×10^{-3}	78.08	84.81	19.13	27.60
CPCI	5.0×10^{-3}	118.75	152.90	23.05	37.32
	10.0×10^{-3}	83.79	89.74	21.29	31.48
EDA	4.0×10^{-3}	2.36	2.76	0.272	0.405
	8.0×10^{-3}	2.19	2.57	0.312	0.479
PrDA	4.0×10^{-3}	3.12	3.59	0.445	0.657
	8.0×10^{-3}	3.00	3.08	0.558	0.691

and CP^+ , are found to be higher than the short-chained bivalent alkanediammonium or tetraalkylammonium ions, which reveals that the former ions are preferred more by the clay matrix than the latter. This is probably due to the fact that for the larger organic ions size is more important than charge in determining their affinity for the aluminosilicate

surface¹⁰ since the dispersion forces increase significantly with the length of the carbon chain. This apart, the solubility of the organic cations in aqueous medium decreases as the size increases, and so there is less tendency for the larger organic ions, once adsorbed, to desorb back into the solution phase⁸.

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